

**EVALUATION OF PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS AND PHYTOCONSTITUENTS
OF SIDDHA FORMULATION KUNMAATHY KUDINEER FOR ANTI-ULCER
POTENTIAL**

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ABSTRACT

Traditional Siddha therapeutics continue to hold significant value in the management of gastrointestinal ailments. Kunmaathy Kudineer is a classical herbal decoction extensively prescribed for “Kunmam,” a condition clinically correlated with peptic ulcer disease, characterized by symptoms such as epigastric pain, dyspepsia, and gastric irritation. The present investigation was undertaken to establish the standardization profile of Kunmaathy Kudineer through systematic evaluation of its physicochemical parameters, phytochemical constituents, and safety aspects in accordance with the guidelines of the Pharmacopoeial Laboratory for Indian Medicine (PLIM). The formulation was prepared using authenticated raw drugs and subjected to comprehensive analytical studies, including organoleptic assessment, physicochemical evaluation (moisture content, ash values, extractive values, and pH), and particle size determination. Safety analysis involved the detection of heavy metals using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), microbial load, specific pathogens, pesticide residues, and aflatoxins. Preliminary phytochemical screening was carried out to identify the presence of bioactive compounds. The analytical findings revealed that the formulation complies with acceptable quality standards, with loss on drying (11.27%), total ash (1.13%), and pH (6.1), indicating stability and suitability for therapeutic use. Phytochemical evaluation indicated the presence of alkaloids, phenols, tannins, saponins, steroids, and triterpenoids, which are known for their anti-ulcer, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. Safety studies demonstrated the absence of microbial contamination, pathogens, pesticide residues, and aflatoxins, while heavy metals were within permissible limits. This study provides scientific evidence supporting the quality, safety, and purity of Kunmaathy Kudineer, thereby validating its traditional application in peptic ulcer management. However, further pharmacological and clinical investigations are required to confirm its therapeutic efficacy.

KEYWORDS: Kunmaathy Kudineer, Siddha medicine, Peptic ulcer.

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, there has been an increasing global inclination toward traditional systems of medicine, emphasizing the necessity for scientific validation and quality standardization of herbal formulations. Among these, the Siddha system of medicine is one of the oldest indigenous healthcare practices, which focuses on maintaining the equilibrium of the three vital humors—Vatham, Pitham, and Kabam—along with the five basic elements and body constituents. Siddha therapeutics

utilizes a wide range of herbal, mineral, and herbo-mineral preparations for disease management. In Siddha literature, conditions analogous to peptic ulcers are described under the term “Kunmam,” which presents with symptoms such as abdominal pain, loss of appetite, indigestion, and general debility. Several classical formulations have been recommended for its treatment, among which Kunmaathy Kudineer is widely recognized for its potential gastroprotective and therapeutic properties. Despite its extensive traditional usage, the

acceptance of such formulations in modern healthcare systems necessitates proper standardization and quality control. Standardization ensures the identity, purity, safety, and efficacy of herbal medicines through detailed physicochemical, phytochemical, and microbiological analyses. Established guidelines by organizations such as the Pharmacopoeial Laboratory for Indian Medicine (PLIM) and the World Health Organization (WHO) provide a structured approach for ensuring consistency and reliability in herbal drug evaluation. Hence, the present study aims to standardize Kunmaathy Kudineer by assessing its physicochemical characteristics, identifying its phytochemical constituents, and evaluating its safety profile. This scientific validation supports its traditional claims and promotes its potential integration into contemporary medical practices.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

PRIMARY

To standardize the drug of *KUNMAATHY KUDINEER* as per the PLIM guidelines.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Table 1: Ingredients of *Kunmaathy Kudineer*.

S.No	Name of drug	Tamil Name	Botanical Name	Parts Used
1.	<i>Ayilyamarapattai</i>	<i>Ayil</i>	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i>	Bark
2.	<i>Pungampattai</i>	<i>Pungu</i>	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Bark
3.	<i>Saaranaiver</i>	<i>Saaranai</i>	<i>Trianthema decandra</i>	Root
4.	<i>Kodiveli ver</i>	<i>Kodiveli</i>	<i>Plumbago indica</i>	Root
5.	<i>Dried Ginger</i>	<i>Chukku</i>	<i>Zingiber officinalis</i>	Rizome
6.	<i>Milagu</i>	<i>Milagu</i>	<i>Piper nigrum</i>	Fruit
7.	<i>Thippili</i>	<i>Thippili</i>	<i>Piper longum</i>	Fruit
8.	<i>Indhuppu</i>	<i>Indhuppu</i>	sodium chloride impura	
9.	<i>Kadukkai Thol</i>	<i>Kadukkai</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Thol

PROCESS OF PREPARATION

All the above ingredients take equal weight of these, grind them into two pieces, and then mixed thoroughly then boiled with sufficient amount of water 16 times and the decoction is reduced to 1/8 of the total mixture and filtered, use it as drinking water at night.

SECONDARY

To evaluate the efficacy of the drug as per the literature.

STUDY METHODOLOGY

STUDY DESIGN

Observation and Analytical study as per the PLIM guidelines.

STUDY PLACE

1. Gunapadam Laboratory, Govt. Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai.
2. Noble Research Solution, Perambur, Chennai.

AUTHENTICATION OF RAW DRUG

The identification of Plant origin drug is authenticated by the PG Gunapadam department, Government siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ORGANOLEPTIC CHARACTERS

Organoleptic characters reveal that EM is hard solid with smooth surface brownish in colour, mild characteristic in odour.

Fig. 1: *Kunmaathy Kudineer Chooranam*.

Table 2: Organoleptic Characters.

State	Solid
Nature	Course
Odor	Characteristic
Touch / Consistency	Hard fibrous
Flow Property	Non Free flowing
Appearance	Brownish

Table 3: Solubility Profile.

S.No	Solvent Used	Solubility / Dispensability
1	Chloroform	Insoluble
2	Ethanol	Soluble
3	Water	Soluble
4	Ethyl acetate	Insoluble
5	DMSO	Soluble

Table 4: Physicochemical Parameters.

S.No	Parameter	Mean (n=3) SD
1.	Loss on Drying at 105 °C (%)	11.27 ± 0.68
2.	Total Ash (%)	1.13 ± 0.13
3.	Acid insoluble Ash (%)	0 ± 0
4.	Water soluble Extractive (%)	12.5 ± 0.26
5.	Alcohol Soluble Extractive (%)	7.567 ± 0.81
6.	pH	6.1

Fig. 2: Microscopic Observation of Particle Size for the sample KUNMAATHY KUDINEER.**REPORT**

Microscopic observation of the particle size analysis reveals that the average particle size of the sample was found to be $87.8 \pm 35.2 \mu\text{m}$.

Table 5: Results For Specific Pathogen.

Organism	Specification	Result	Method
<i>E-coli</i>	Absent	Absent	As per AYUSH specification
<i>Salmonella</i>	Absent	Absent	
<i>Staphylococcus Aureus</i>	Absent	Absent	
<i>Pseudomonas Aeruginosa</i>	Absent	Absent	

No growth / colonies were observed in any of the plates inoculated with the test sample.

Fig. 3: Culture plate with *E-coli* (EC) specific medium.

Fig. 4: Culture plate with *Salmonella* (SA) specific medium.

Fig. 5. Culture plate with *Staphylococcus Aureus* (ST) specific medium.

Fig. 6. Culture plate with *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* (PS) specific medium.

PESTICIDE RESIDUE

The result shows that there were no traces of pesticides residues such as Organochlorine, Organophosphorus,

Organocarbamates and pyrethroids in the sample provided for analysis.

Fig. 7: Sterility Test By Pour Plate Method.

No growth / colonies was observed in any of the plates inoculated with the test sample.

Table 6: Result for Microbial Contamination.

Test	Result	Specification	As per AYUSH/WHO
Total Bacterial Count	Absent	NMT 10 ⁵ CFU/g	As per AYUSH specification
Total Fungal Count	Absent	NMT 10 ³ CFU/g	

Table 7: Test Results For Pesticide Residues.

Pesticide Residue	Sample KK	AYUSH Limit (mg/kg)
I.Organo Chlorine Pesticides		
Alpha BHC	BQL	0.1mg/kg
Beta BHC	BQL	0.1mg/kg
Gamma BHC	BQL	0.1mg/kg
Delta BHC	BQL	0.1mg/kg
DDT	BQL	1mg/kg
Endosulphan	BQL	3mg/kg
II.Organo Phosphorus Pesticides		
Malathion	BQL	1mg/kg
Chlorpyrifos	BQL	0.2 mg/kg
Dichlorovos	BQL	1mg/kg
III. Organo carbamates		
Carbofuran	BQL	0.1mg/kg
III.Pyrethroid		
Cypermethrin	BQL	1mg/kg

BQL- Below Quantification Limit

PESTICIDE RESIDUES

The result shows that there were no traces of pesticides residues such as Organochlorine, Organophosphorus,

Organocarbamates and pyrethroids in the sample provided for analysis.

Fig.8: Qualitative Phytochemical Evaluation Of Kunmaathy Kudineer.

The Results for the Analysis of phytochemical present in the given sample was mentioned and the outcome were tabulated in table 10.

Phytochemical Analysis of KUNMAATHY KUDINEER

Table 8: Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis of KUNMAATHY KUDINEER.

Phytochemical Analytical Report S.NO	TEST	OBSERVATION
1	ALKALOIDS	+
2	FLAVANOIDS	-
3	GLYCOSIDES	-
4	STEROIDS	+
5	TRITERPENOIDS	+
6	COUMARIN	-
7	PHENOL	+
8	TANIN	+
9	SAPONINS	+
10	PROTEIN	-
11	SUGAR	+
12	ANTHOCYANIN	-
13	BETACYANIN	-

(+)->Indicates Positive and(-)->Indicates Negative

Table 9: TEST FOR ACID RADICALS.

Specific Radical	Test Report
Test for carbonates	Positive- Indicates Presence
Test for chlorides	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for sulfates	Positive- Indicates Presence
Test for sulphides	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for phosphates	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for Fluoride and Oxalate	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for Borates	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for Nitrates	Negative - Indicates Absence

Table 10: Test For Basic Radicals.

Specific Radical	Test Report
Test for Lead	Positive- Indicates Presence
Test for Arsenic	Positive- Indicates Presence
Test for Mercury	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for Copper	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for Ferric	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for Ferrous	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for Zinc	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for Silver	Negative - Indicates Absence
Test for Magnesium	Negative - Indicates Absence

Table 11: Aflatoxin Assay By Tlc.

Aflatoxin	Sample KK	AYUSH Specification Limit
B1	Not Detected - Absent	0.5 ppm (0.5mg/kg)
B2	Not Detected - Absent	0.1 ppm (0.1mg/kg)
G1	Not Detected - Absent	0.5 ppm (0.5mg/kg)
G2	Not Detected - Absent	0.1 ppm (0.1mg/kg)

The results shown that there were no spots were being identified in the test sample loaded on TLC plates when compare to the standard which indicates that the sample were free from Aflatoxin B1, Aflatoxin B2, Aflatoxin G1 and Aflatoxin G2.

DISCUSSION

The present study established the standardization profile of Kunmaathy Kudineer through organoleptic, physicochemical, phytochemical, and safety evaluations. The formulation exhibited characteristic organoleptic properties, appearing as a brownish solid with a mild odor, indicating uniformity and proper preparation.

Solubility analysis showed that the drug is soluble in water, ethanol, and DMSO, suggesting better dissolution and potential enhancement of oral bioavailability. The loss on drying (11.27%) reflects acceptable moisture content, while the total ash value (1.13%) indicates minimal inorganic impurities, confirming the quality of the formulation. Extractive values revealed the presence of significant bioactive constituents, and the slightly acidic pH (6.1) suggests compatibility with gastric conditions.

Safety assessment demonstrated that heavy metals such as lead and arsenic were within permissible limits, indicating the formulation is safe for therapeutic use. Microbial analysis confirmed the absence of pathogenic organisms, including *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Additionally, no pesticide residues or aflatoxins were detected, ensuring purity and compliance with AYUSH and WHO standards.

Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of key bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, phenols, tannins, saponins, steroids, and triterpenoids. These constituents are known for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, gastroprotective, and anti-ulcer activities. The presence of these compounds supports the traditional use of the formulation in managing Kunmam (peptic ulcer) by enhancing mucosal defense and reducing oxidative stress.

Overall, the findings confirm that Kunmaathy Kudineer meets standard quality parameters and possesses significant therapeutic potential. However, further pharmacological and clinical studies are required to validate its efficacy in peptic ulcer management.

CONCLUSION

The results of the present investigation confirm that the Siddha formulation Kunmaathy Kudineer possesses potent biologically active components that may contribute to the treatment of various disorders, particularly Kunmam (peptic ulcer). Standardization using modern analytical tools such as physicochemical, phytochemical, profiling has provided a scientific basis for its purity, safety, and efficacy. This study has generated evidence-based data on the standardization of Kunmaathy Kudineer, which can serve as a reference for future quality control and validation studies. However, further *in vivo* and clinical investigations are essential to confirm its therapeutic efficacy and establish its role as a reliable Siddha medicine for clinical practice.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The Author declares no conflict of interest.

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